

Microscopic Use-wear Analysis of the lithic assemblages from Ullafelsen and Kaseralmschrofen, Fotschertal, Tyrol

Abstract

A microscopic use-wear analysis was conducted on lithic artefacts of two sites in the Tyrolean Fotsch Valley, Ullafelsen and Kaseralmschrofen. 82 artefacts from Ullafelsen and 22 from Kaseralmschrofen were subjected to high and low power analysis. Different edge damage patterns, micropolishes and organic residues are interpreted in order to reconstruct the former use of stone tools. The analysis complements a previous traceological study of the modified lithic artefacts from Ullafelsen. Almost one fourth of the unmodified debitage and lithic fragments from Ullafelsen had use-wear traces and could be identified as used tools and fragments thereof. Those unmodified tools were a significant addition to the lithic toolkit at Ullafelsen and were used similarly to the modified artefacts. Wear traces could be detected on the majority of the analysed artefacts from Kaseralmschrofen. The activities identified on the lithic tools from both sites were mostly associated with the repair and maintenance of the hunting gear and the processing of hide and leather.

Methods

The same methods and instruments used for the functional analysis of the tools and modified artefacts of Ullafelsen (Pawlik 2011) were applied for the second stage of the functional studies of this early Mesolithic assemblage. It was aimed at the analysis of the unmodified pieces from Ullafelsen, including several refitted artefacts and the assemblage of the site Kaseralmschrofen located approximately in ca. 700m distance from Ullafelsen following the Fotsch River downhill.

The so-called Low Power Analysis was conducted with a Nikon SMZ stereo-microscope and a magnification range of 6-60x. For High Power Analysis, an Olympus BHMJ reflected light microscope operating with differential interference contrast after Nomarski (DIC/NIC) and long-working-distance objectives (LWD) was used, offering magnifications of 110x, 220x and 440x. Microphotographic documentation of the observed wear traces was performed using digital cameras, a Nikon D200 DSLR for low power, and a Canon Powershot G9 for high power photography. Both cameras were connected to a personal computer and remotely controlled with dedicated image capture software.

Prior to High Power analysis, all artefacts were cleaned in an ultrasonic tank and a mild solution of dishwashing liquid and distilled water, and consequently rinsed in a 50% alcohol solution. This procedure cleans artefacts for microscopic analysis gently and efficiently without leaving stains on the artefact surface or causing damage to residues (Unrath et al. 1986).

Glossary

PUA – Potentially Used Area

PDSM- Post-depositional surface modifications

Residues – smallest amounts of the contact materials located on artefact surfaces

Second-edge-row – Secondary row of microscars located on larger, primary edge scars and retouches. Patrick Vaughan's (1985) experiments demonstrated that second-edge-rows are an indicator for hard contact materials

Striations – microscopic scratches and grooves on the surfaces of micropolishes that allow the determination of the direction of movement of the tool
 Superficial striations – linear micropolishes (Fischer et al. 1984)
 Contact surface – the tool’s surface facing the worked material
 Non-contact surface – the tool’s surface turned away from the worked material
 Micropitting – microscopic depressions in the polish surface, appearing like stitches of a needle.
 Potlids – diffuse, crater-like depressions in the polish surface
 Reticular pattern – Micropolish is formed in a net-like pattern on the elevated areas of the tool’s microtopography
 GWP – Generic weak polish, following Vaughan’s (1985) three-stage-model it is the initial stage of micropolish development
 SPP – Smooth-pitted polish, following Vaughan’s three-stage-model it is the intermediate stage of micropolish development
 WDP – Well-developed polish, following Vaughan’s three-stage-model it is the final stage of micropolish development

The terminology of the described edge wear generally follows Hayden 1979 and Vaughan 1985 (Figure 1, Table 1)

Table 1: Abbreviations of scar cross-sections used in this chapter (after Vaughan 1985)

proximal cross-section	Abbrev.	distal cross-section	Abbrev.
Shallow	PSH	Feather	DFR
Break-Shallow	PBS	Step	DST
Steep	PST	Hinge	DHG
Crescent Break	CB	Crescent Break	CB

z.B. PST = Proximal steep; DHG = Distal Hinge

1 Unretouched artefacts from Ullafelsen with wear traces

1.1 Artefacts made of Rofan material:

B8-99 (Figure 2a): This elongated flake has several areas with edge scarring. Area A on dorsal is a steep notch consisting of stepped DST- and DHG scars. The scarring has a strong similarity with experimentally created trampling traces (see Unrath et al., 1986) and might not be related to actual use (Figure 2b, Area A). At Area B, an edge row composed of bidirectional and transverse scars, mainly with PST-DHG cross-sections appears in the proximal part of the tool. Those traces point to a longitudinal motion of the edge and probably related to a cutting activity (Figure 2c). Only few micropolish spots appear. They are poorly developed and don’t provide much information. The opposite edge shows as well edge scarring with a sequence of partially overlapping DFR-negatives. They appear on dorsal (Figure 2d, Area C) and at Area D on ventral (Figure 2e). Area E has a stepped appearance due to pronounced Wallner lines and possesses few scars (Figure 2f). Its immediate edge has slightly rounding visible at higher magnification (Figure 2g) and a rough and rumpled GWP micropolish (Pos. 1, Figure 2h). The small flake was possibly used as an expedient tool for cutting softer to middle hard materials. No traces of hafting appeared.

B8-257 (Figure 3a): This flake shows few scars on its distal end that might be the remains of a retouch (Figure 3b, Area A). At Area B, the distal end is reduced by several crescent breaks (Figure 3c). The lateral edge PUA I is mostly undamaged while some scars with PST-DFR cross-section were observed along the opposite steep angled edge (Figure 3d, Area C). Despite the scarring, no distinctive use-wear traces were identified and no micropolishes were detected on the rather fresh appearing surfaces. The slight edge damage seems therefore post-depositional and not use-related.

C5-482 (Figure 4a): This bent and slightly twisted microflake is probably a burin spall. Despite its bent shape remained the lateral edge PUA I rather straight. A sequence of evenly shaped microscars appears along the acute-angled sharp edge, mainly on dorsal (Figure 4b, Area A). Their cross-sections are dominantly flat with step and feather terminations. Single larger PST-DFR negatives and crescent breaks can be seen ventral on Area C (Figure 4c). A strong patination compromised the power analysis, although dull GWP polishes are still visible at the proximal end (Figure 4d, Pos. 1). The distal end features better developed micropolishes with domed appearance and diffuse micropitting (Figure 4e, Pos. 4). The lateral edge PUA I has bright polish spots with a domed and rough surface structure present, foremost on elevated parts of the micro-topography (Figure 4f, Pos. 2). They point towards a use of this edge. On the same edge appear several bright spots (Levi-Sala 1998), caused by non-intentional contact with other siliceous artefacts (Figure 4g, Pos. 3). This might indicate that either the burin spall or, more likely, the entire burin prior to the spall's removal was kept and/or carried together with other tools, for example in a pouch. Blackish residues from hafting adhesive appear on the scars on dorsal and ventral (Figure 4h, Area B). They also appear within the corners of the dorsal reduction negatives (Figure 4i, Area D) and suggest the use of the spatula-like proximal end to clean out a hafting slot from remaining adhesive perhaps in connection with hafting-and-retooling. A similar function can be considered for the distal end as well while the edge wear of Area A was more likely caused by a longitudinal activity, i.e. cutting. The opposite lateral edge does not show any signs of use.

C7-23 (Figure 5a): This elongated flake carries a rather thick base and a pointed distal end. No use-wear appears on its lateral edges (Figure 5b, Area A) while the distal end shows a transverse shear fracture that removed most of the immediate tip (Figure 5c, Area B). The lateral break resembles a burin facet. Its rather fresh-looking surface points to a post-depositional cause (Figure 5d, Pos. 3). Only weak polishes in vaguely visible longitudinal orientation and diffuse striations are detected on the tip (Figure 5e, Pos. 1). The basal area carries residues that appear like pitch on the lateral part and on the dorsal platform reduction (Figure 5f, Area C; Figure 5g, Area D). Solidified drops of pitch are visible on ventral under higher magnification (Figure 5h, Area E). Associated with the residues are reticular polish patterns typical for contacts with a shaft (Figure 5i, Pos. 2). Hafting of the base can be assumed, especially since no residues appear on the tool's medial and distal area. The damage of the tip is, on the other hand, the result of a hard impact and together with the hafting traces identify this artefact as a projectile point.

C7-36 (Figure 6a): This is a trapezoidal flake with a straight, sharp-angled edge of ca. 27 mm length at its distal end. Different forms of scars appear along the edge. The dorsal face shows a row of minuscule microscars with PST-DFR cross-sections along Area A (Figure 6b), interrupted by larger scars with PST-DFR and CB cross-sections and with perpendicular and transverse orientation (Figure 6c, Area B; 6d, Area C). Generic weak polish created a bevel-like band along the ventral side of the edge (Figure 6e, Pos. 1). Several diffuse striations perpendicular to the edge indicate a frontal force (Figure 6f, Pos. 2). No wear traces were found on the lateral edges. The proximal part of the tool has pitch residues on dorsal and on the butt (Figure 6g, Area D; Figure 6h, Area E), pointing towards a basal hafting of the flake. Abrasions

on the dorsal ridge might have caused by slight rubbing contacts with the shaft (Figure 6i, Pos. 3). While a function as a scraper-like instrument is not entirely impossible, the weak development of edge wear and micropolish suggest that this trapezoidal flake was more likely used as a transverse projectile head.

C9-649 (Figure 7a): This artefact is a fragment of a microblade with oblique distal end. The proximal part was removed by a hinge fracture and is missing in the assemblage. This part carries residues of hafting pitch (Figure 7b, Area A; Figure 7c, Pos. 2) that continue along the lateral edge where several residue spots can be found, for example medial at Area B (Figure 7d) and at the distal end at Area C (Figure 7e). Both lateral edges seem mostly undamaged while larger scars occur on both ends. A large negative with hinge termination that seems to be the result of a hard impact reduced the proximal part (Figure 7f, Area D), while the distal end was shattered by a sequence of scars with PST-DHG cross-sections (Figure 7g, Area E; Figure 7h, Area F). The scars resulted from direct impact, respectively were caused by reacting force. Linear oriented micropolish and diffuse striations in the same longitudinal direction support this assumption (Figure 7i, Pos. 1). The traces indicate that this tool was used as a hafted projectile implement. Intensely reflecting bright spots on the dorsal ridge suggest that this flake (or its core prior to removal) had contacts with other siliceous artefacts (Figure 7j, Pos. 3) and was probably carried together with other tools for considerable time.

1.2 Artefacts made of Frankenalb hornstone:

B5-200 (Figure 8a): Both faces of this microflake are covered with residues of streaky appearance (Figure 8b). The lateral edges are mostly without wear traces (Figure 8c, Pos. 4) while the proximal end and the butt show intensive scarring and shattering, more than what is usually related to the knapping process (Figure 8d, Area A). On ventral, the bulb was removed by a frontal impact coming from the proximal end (Figure 8e, Area B). The pointed distal end exhibits several small frontal scars with DHG and DST terminations, similar to short burin facets (Figure 8f, Area C). The immediate distal end has been reduced by a large and transverse oriented crescent break (Figure 8g, Area D). Near the tip appear different kinds of residues, red-coloured with amorphous structure (Figure 8h, Area E, Figure 8i, Pos. 1) and blackish pitch residues still containing primary organic matter under the reflected light microscope (Figure 8j). Despite the similar appearance of the red coloured residues a test for blood stains was negative. Instead, they are probably the remains of brown algae or Phaeophytes, and not resulting from use (Werner Pflug¹, pers. comm. 2009). Micropolishes with a coarse surface structure appear on elevated areas of the microtopography like edges and ridges of scars, and as a result of a contact with a shaft (Figure 8k, Pos. 2; Figure 8l, Pos. 3). The observed wear traces indicate the use of this tool as a projectile point. The reduction of the bulb might have served to fit the tool in an already existing hafting slot.

B5-395,1 – 2 (Figure 9a): These are two blades from the same context and found in close proximity that could be refitted. Bladelet no. B5-395,2 connects to the dorsal face of the blade no. B5-392,1. This blade has irregular and not very intensive scarring along both lateral edges (Area A-C, Figure 9b, 9c). caused by scars with PSH-DHG cross-sections in perpendicular and transverse direction. Limited micropolish has formed on both edges in form of dull linear polishes with diffuse striations more or less parallel to the edge (Figure 9d, Pos. 1). Pitch residues are present on the dorsal and ventral faces of both edges, especially on proximal and the striking platform remnant (Figure 9e, Area D; Figure 9f, Area E), as well as on ventral until

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the distal end (Figure 9g, Area F, Figure 9h, Area G). The negative face of the refitted bladelet B5-395,2, however, doesn't show any wear traces and (Figure 9i, Pos. 2) almost no residues. Only at the distal end appear smallest amounts of hafting adhesive (Figure 9j, Area H). This observation is in accordance with the similarly clean ventral face of B5-395,2 (Figure 9k, Pos. 3) that shows only few residue streaks on the coarse surface of the proximal part and appears unused (Figure 9l, Area I). In addition, the lateral edges do not show any signs of use. This suggests that B5-395,2 was still attached to B395,1 during its use and hafting, although an initial fracture in form of a hairline crack where the liquid pitch could have penetrated the tool might have existed. During its use and probably caused by one or more hard impacts, the initial crack widened and finally separated the bladelet from the larger blade. Held in place by the pitch adhesive, the fragments remained in the hafting slot probably until they were removed after returning to the base camp of Ullafelsen, and discarded at the same spot.

B5-396 (Figure 10a): This thin and fragile bladelet possesses sharp lateral edges and a protruded and jagged proximal end without any traces of edge damage. However, residue streaks with adhering sediment particles appear on both faces (Figure 10b, Area A) up to the level of visible brush-stroke patterns (Figure 10c-e, Area B-D). They were not caused by the cleaning procedure that was applied to this artefact (pers. comm. D. Schäfer, 2010) but can be considered as primary traces that indicate a hafted use. Dense micropolish exhibiting a coarse and rumpled structure created a bevel at the tip of the bladelet (Figure 10f, Pos. 1), while the tip itself shows distinct rounding. Micropolish and rounding indicate the working of a softer but abrasive material. Short delicate linear polishes and striations in longitudinal orientation appear at the tip on dorsal (Figure 10g, Pos. 2) suggesting the use of this tool as an awl-like instrument for the processing of hide and leather.

B6: 163 (Figure 11a): This ridge blade is composed of two refitted fragments that broke apart after deposition. It has a cortex coverage of approx. 40%. The distal part has a steep hinge termination and is of triangular shape. No edge wear is visible. Comparison of the surfaces of both fragments clearly indicates separation prior to the use of the larger fragment. While the medial area shows WDP micropolish, the connecting proximal part remained without any microwear (Figure 11b, Pos. 1). The larger proximal-medial part has a row of scars along the lateral edge PUA I (Figure 11c, Area A). They are irregularly shaped and directed perpendicular and transverse to the edge (Figure 11d, Area B). Short-wide negatives with DST- und DHG-cross-sections that partially notched the edge are dominating (Figure 11e, Area C), also few scars with PSH-DFR-cross-section occur. The larger scars are mostly on the dorsal face, ventral shows groups of fine retouches, instead (Figure 11f, Area D). PUA I is covered by micropolishes of a smudgy and dull appearance (Figure 11g, Pos. 2; Figure 11h, Pos. 5). They form a reticular pattern at the proximal end (Figure 11i, Pos. 3) that intensifies to a well-connected polish at Pos. 4 (Figure 11j). The traces point to a longitudinal activity. The irregular and not very intense edge scarring suggests the cutting of softer materials while the reticular micropolish was probably caused by occasional contacts with a hard base, similar to a cut board. The cortex covered lateral edge does not have any traces of actual use but could have served as a grip. However, pitch residues are located around the butt area on dorsal (Figure 11k, Area E) and ventral (Figure 11l, Area F). Therefore, it is also possible that the tool was hafted at its proximal base.

C5: 517 (Figure 12a): Almost no use-wear can be recognized on this elongated and pointed flake. Only the tip exhibits trapezoidal and shallow scars with DST terminations perpendicular and transverse to the edge (Figure 12b, Area A; Figure 12c, Area B). They correspond with PST-DFR scars on the dorsal face at Area C and a very delicate fine retouch until the distal end (Figure 12d, Area D). A sequence of trapezoidal scars with step and hinge terminations appears

in opposite direction to the scars of Area D on the dorsal ridge (Figure 12e, Area E). The immediate tip was removed by a shear fracture. Weakly developed micropolish with a smudgy and rumpled structure and blunt reflection point to the working of a softer material (Figure 12f, Pos. 1). No micropolish was detected beyond the tip except for several bright spots on Pos. 2 that were very likely caused by non-intentional contacts with other siliceous artefacts (Figure 12g). Distribution and direction of the wear traces suggest a use of this artefact as a perforator. It was probably discarded after the tip broke off.

C6: 28 (Figure 13a): The edges of this flake exhibit wear traces. PUA I has a row of negatives with PST-DFR cross-sections (Figure 13b, Area A) and a partially developed second-edge-row, respectively a delicate row of steep scars facing ventral at Area B (Figure 13c). The ventral face, however, has no micropolish while a polish bevel and a reticular polish pattern can be found on dorsal (Figure 13d, Pos. 3). A group of PSH-DST scars appears opposite of Area A on the dorsal face, in perpendicular orientation to the edge (Figure 13e, Area C). PUA II shows several secondary scars mainly with hinge terminations along the burin facet-like reduction. (Figure 13f, Area D). At Area E, scars appear also on ventral (Figure 13g) and are associated with mostly poorly developed reticular polish patterns (Figure 13h, Pos. 1). Only few isolated polish spots show a better developed SPP structure and bright reflection (Figure 13i, Pos. 2) indicating a harder organic contact material. At Area F appears a delicate retouch together with larger scalar scars on PUA I (Figure 13j). Blackish residues, probably the remains of hafting pitch, are found within the corners of the scars while several residue streaks appear on ventral, for example at Area G (Figure 13k). Remains of a modern glue together with some blue textile fibres can be found on this piece as well, probably deriving from the accessioning and labelling of this artefact (Figure 13l, Area H). The use traces were caused by a less intensive, transversely oriented activity. The distribution of micropolish along PUA I indicates that dorsal was hereby the contact surface, while PUA II ventral served as contact face. Residues within the use scars suggest the maintenance of used and pitch covered wooden shafts, including scraping and smoothing as part of hafting-and-retooling activities.

C6: 118 (Figure 14a): This flake displays a faint row of microscars along its convex lateral edge located at Areas A and B, separated by a medial notch. It is composed of semi- steep DFR negatives mostly located on the dorsal face (Figure 14b). A small micropolish bevel appears as well along the edge (Figure 14c, Pos. 1). The polish has a bright reflection, domed structure and diffuse micropitting. and is developed mainly on the protruding parts of the edge. (Figure 14d, Pos. 2). The overall limited appearance of wear traces suggests a short-term, ad-hoc use of this edge, possibly a scraping or smoothing activity on a middle-hard material.

C6: 122 (Figure 15a): This elongated flake displays visible edge scarring along its straight edge PUA I. Particularly, the distal part of PUA I appears serrated, caused by steep scars with DFR- and DST-terminations as well as crescent breaks (Figure 15b, Area A; Figure 15c, Area B). These negatives are appearing on dorsal and ventral in transverse and perpendicular orientation. The proximal part of the edge shows similar edge wear; however, negatives DFR-terminations are dominant, and they are smaller and more regular (Figure 15d, Area C). Morphology and distribution of the scars point to a longitudinal activity, for example cutting or sawing. The observed micropolishes support this interpretation. Despite being rather weakly developed, their reticular distribution pattern on elevated parts of the microtopography and their micropitting structure are diagnostic features of a harder organic material (Figure 15e, Pos. 1). Frontal scars on ventral and dorsal on Area D suggest that the pointed distal end was also part of the functional area of the tool (Figure 15f, Area D).

C8: 1209 (Figure 16a): This flake carries considerable amounts of pitch residues at its pointed proximal end. Visible rounding occurs around the pointed platform remnant (Figure 16b, Area A), as well as shallow scars with DST terminations on ventral (Figure 16c, Area B). Residues can be observed on the medial part of PUA I, associated with scalar scars in transverse direction on ventral (Figure 16d, Area C). On dorsal, a linear, streak-like appearance of the residues is visible (Figure 16e, Area D). More residues appear within a hinged, burin-like notch at Area E, although less preserved (Figure 16f). While it is not certain whether this scar and its residue deposit are use-related, the tool's tip and the lateral edge PUA I were certainly functionally active parts. The tip was possibly used for scraping off pitch remains from hafting slots during retooling processes. The lateral edge could have been used for scraping or smoothing a harder organic material, perhaps the wooden shafts themselves. The limited development of wear traces indicates a rather brief period of use. The thinner distal end is irregularly broken and still very sharp. The break appears to be post-depositional and not related to the tool's function.

D5: 347 (Figure 17a): This blade fragment is largely covered with cortex, except for the lateral edge PUA I. Its distal and proximal ends were removed. The cortex covered lateral edge PUA II has a delicate burin facet as sole modification (Figure 17b, Area A). It shows no wear traces and appears more like an impact scar. PUA I possesses few irregular negatives and areas with delicate microscars with DFR termination. They seem to be non-intentional damages, probably caused by the handling of this tool (Figure 17c, Area B; Figure 17d, Area C). The distal end initially formed as a finial and has been modified with a steep retouch. They are covered with pitch residues, especially on the part facing PUA II (Figure 17e, Area D). A similar residue appearance can be seen at proximal (Figure 17f, Area E). The porous cortex shows a higher degree of staining with a mix of residues and sediment particles along PUA II, with spot-like residues scattered on the entire cortex area (Figure 17g, Area F). In contrast, very few residues appear on the smooth ventral face and the lateral edge PUA I. It can be assumed that this tool was a laterally hafted projectile implement with PUA I as the functionally active edge while PUA II was placed within a shaft. The burin-like impact scar on PUA II could be a result of reacting forces within the haft. Probably, this damage led to the discarding of the implement since no residues appear on the scar's facet.

D5: 1229 (Figure 18a): This is a small flake with a partial retouch of its convex distal end (Figure 18b, Area A). The steep modification resembles a scraper retouch. Its negatives are located on dorsal while the edge appears on ventral slightly rounded (Figure 18c, Area B). High power analysis reveals a moderately developed polish bevel with a coarse and smudgy appearance (Figure 18d, Pos. 1). Furthermore, short diffuse striations developed on a rumpled GWP matrix in transverse orientation to the edge (Figure 18e, Pos. 2). Several burin-like removals initiating from proximal tapered the artefact and gave it a tanged appearance (Figure 18f, Area C). The "tang" shows pitch residues that appear mainly on the fissured dorsal face (Figure 18g, Area D), but are also seen on ventral (Figure 18h, Area E; Figure 18i, Area F). The traces indicate a use of this flake as a scraper-like instrument, hafted along the tanged proximal part. The slight rounding of the scraper's edge and the micropolish structure point towards a softer but tenacious contact material like hide and leather.

1.3 Artefacts made of South-Alpine Flint

B5: 231 (Figure 19a): Both lateral edges of this blade-like flake exhibit minor scarring. The distal part of the longer PUA I has a slightly denticulated edge caused by alternating PBS-DFR scars (Figure 19b, Area A). On proximal, trapezoidal and scalar PBS-DFR negatives are dominating, appearing mostly on the dorsal face (Figure 19c, Area B). Some scars are covered with pitch residues (Figure 19d). More residues can be observed on Area F (Figure 19h). PUA

II shows a coarse indentation at its distal end caused by several crescent breaks and very steep PST-scars (Figure 19e, Area C). This damage seems to be non-intentional. The remaining edge carries proximally a fine and regular shaped retouch with PST-DFR negatives on dorsal (Figure 19f, Area D). On ventral, the scars appear in different sizes and shapes but mainly with PSH-DFR/DST cross-sections (Figure 19g, Area E). The remaining distal end has frontal impact scars with PBS-DFR cross-sections (Figure 19i, Area G). The tool was probably hafted along its lateral edge PUA II. The scars on PUA I indicate a use in longitudinal motion while the frontal scars at the distal end and the indentation suggest a use as projectile implement.

B5: 435 (Figure 20a): This medial blade fragment displays wear traces on its lateral edge PUA I and on the distal end. PUA I has a row of delicate microscars with steep PST-DFR cross-sections on ventral (Figure 20b, Area A). A slight abrasion of the immediate edge is caused by a second-edge-row. On ventral, two large scalar scars with DFR-termination are clearly recognized by their fresh surface appearance as post-depositional (Figure 20c, Area B). The remaining part of the lateral edge appears more or less undamaged. The opposite lateral edge has a 90° edge angle and resembles a burin facet. No edge scarring is visible. However, delicate burin blows appear on the break surface at the distal end at Area C (Figure 20d). The immediate tip is abraded by successive DHG-scars (Figure 20e). Here, and on the burin facet are minor pitch residues located. The opposite corner Area D is slightly blunted by PST-DFR scars (Figure 20f). The retouch stretches over the corner into the lateral edge and seems there a bit rounded (Figure 20g). The surfaces of this tool have a glossy appearance, making it unsuitable for high power analysis while the limited edge wear prevents a more detailed functional interpretation of the artefact. In context with the few residues and the location of the wear, a use for hafting/retooling purposes, e.g. for cleaning used hafting slots, seems possible.

B6: 20 (Figure 21a): A blade-like flake with a tipped distal end. Several burin removals appear on PUA I that produced an almost perpendicularly angled, robust edge. The edge of the burin facet has on ventral shallow trapezoidal scars with DST-terminations. A second-edge-row formed along their edges (Figure 21b, Area A). The traces were probably caused by a transversely oriented activity or by the blunting of the protruding sharp edge. An indication for the latter might be the presence of pitch residues on the burin facet as well as the absence of any other edge damage (Figure 21c, Area B). The residues appear along the entire edge and indicate a lateral hafting of the tool. The convex edge PUA II has on dorsal at its medial part an irregular retouch (Figure 21d, Area C). Several burin-like frontal scars with DST- and DHG-cross-sections appear on dorsal at the distal end (Figure 21e, Area D; Figure 21f, Area E). Similar removals appear as well on ventral (Figure 21g, Area F). A glossy post-depositional “sediment polish” prevented the high-power analysis (Figure 21h, Pos. 1). Nevertheless, the various impact scars and traces of hafting suggest that this artefact was used as a laterally hafted projectile implement.

C6: 4 (Figure 22a): On this large elongated burin spall with triangular cross-section, traces of wear appear mainly on its pointed distal end. Several irregular scalar PSH-DST scars initiated from the dorsal ridge are situated towards the right burin edge (Figure 22b, Area A). The ridge itself shows abrasion caused by a sequence of short-wide microscars with DHG cross-sections. (Figure 22c, Area B). On ventral, a series of microscars corresponds with the dorsal wear traces, thus pointing to a revolving motion (Figure 22d, Area C). Near the tip appear pitch residues, especially where the surface has a rougher texture (Figure 22e, Area D), or where former microfossils and crystals left small cavities (Figure 22f, Area E). On the wider proximal area appear only few shallow residue streaks mainly on the cortex that are likely associated with the

handling of the tool. Its entire surface is covered by a strong “sediment polish” that mostly prevents high power analysis (Figure 22g, Pos. 1). Only at Pos. 2 appears a bright reflecting polish with a blotting paper-like structure and delicate striations in longitudinal direction (Figure 22h). Obviously, the functional part of the tool was its pointed distal end. The adhering pitch residues suggest hafting/retooling activities, possibly associated with the cleaning and modification of used hafting slots. Another use as perforator is possible, but cannot be securely determined by the rather limited wear traces.

D5: 344 (Figure 23a): This rather large blade shows traces of wear along all its edges. A glossy sediment polish that seems typical for this raw material prevents a high power analysis (Figure 23b, Pos. 1) and restricts the analysis to the low power method. Here, a delicate serrated row of scars with PST-DFR cross-section together with some crescent breaks appears along PUA I and mainly on the ventral face (Figure 23c, Area A). Similar scars are visible on PUA II. Here, the scars are evenly distributed on both faces (Figure 23d, Area B; Figure 23e, Area C). A row of irregularly shaped PST-DFR scars and crescent breaks serrated the oblique and steep-angled distal end (Figure 23f, Area D). The protruded Area E carries larger scars with DST-termination and an initial second-edge-row (Figure 23g). Both corners of the distal end show as well larger scars in frontal direction but with DST- und DHG cross-sections resembling short impact scars (Figure 23h, Area F; Figure 23i, Area G). The proximal part of the artefact has a shattered appearance with a strong scarring on dorsal that seems to exceed the usual traces caused by the reduction process (Figure 23j, Area H). Longitudinal breaks and fissures appear on the bulbar area and were caused by repetitive hard strikes on the proximal end (Figure 23k, Area J). They are typical for the striking areas of tools used as chisels. The distal end served hereby as functional edge. The lateral edges seem to be functional areas connected to longitudinal activities like cutting.

D5: 588 (Figure 24a): This is an elongated flake with triangular shape and cross-section. Both lateral edges show only slight wear traces. The shallow-angled PUA I bears an irregular row of microscars, predominantly with PST-DFR cross-sections (Figure 24b, Area A). At proximal appear the scars mainly on dorsal (Figure 24c, Area B). Several DST-scars initiated at the distal end have slightly larger sizes, and are transversely and longitudinally oriented to the edge. (Figure 24d, Area C). The distal end shows a shear fracture. A frontal burin-like scar with subsequent fissures was probably caused by a hard impact (Figure 24e, Area D). Pitch residues appear along the entire edge of PUA II but mainly on its proximal part (Figure 24f, Area E). Strong sediment polish prevents high power analysis (Figure 24g, Pos. 1). Nevertheless, the appearance of residues and impact scars permit the interpretation of this artefact as a projectile point with basal hafting.

D7:15 (Figure 25a): This is a burin spall with triangular cross section that was detached from a backed retouched artefact. The distal part ends in a hinge and its slightly protruding lip has been reduced by a row of trapezoidal negatives. They bear minor pitch residues as well as post-depositional pencil marks (Figure 25b, Area A). The lateral edges of this artefact are only slightly jarred and show no sign of use. However, residues occur particularly on the backed retouch and as loosely distributed spots on the smooth surfaces of the bladelet (Figure 25c, Area B). The immediate tip has a frontal damage in form of a long and narrow negative with PBS-DHG cross section (Figure 25d, Area C). Shorter scars appear on ventral, while a delicate row of microscars appears at the flared proximal end (Figure 25e, Area D). The wear traces on the tip suggest its use as an engraving tool. The residues on distal might point to a pencil-like hafting of the pointed artefact.

D8: 21 (Figure 26a): This is an irregular shaped blade with a curved distal section. Its distal end is partially covered with cortex, the other part is damaged by transverse fractures (Figure 26b, Area E). They do not seem to be intentional modifications, and no use scars are visible (Figure 26c, Area A). The proximal end has a tang-like shape, created by few irregular retouches (Figure 26d, Area B; Figure 26e, Area C). Pitch residues appear on the proximal section, including the platform remnant (Figure 26f, Area D). The residues might not be the remains of a basal hafting due to the missing functional character of the corresponding distal end but are rather resulting from a use of the proximal part for the maintenance of pitch covered shafts and hafting slots.

Despite the curved longitudinal shape of the blade, the lateral edge PUA I is mostly straight and carries fairly steep transverse and diagonal scars with dominantly PBS-DFR cross sections. They appear mainly on dorsal (Figure 26g, Area F) but also on ventral together with trapezoidal PSH-DST scars (Figure 26h, Area G). No second-edge-row developed. The edge was obviously used for transverse, scraping activities with ventral as the main contact face, and occasionally for longitudinal actions like cutting. Similar edge scarring is observed on the curved PUA II with the scars appearing mainly on ventral. A row of PST-DFR negatives with regular shapes formed on the distal part (Figure 26i, Area H). They are followed by scalar PBS-DFR and trapezoidal PSH-DFR scars which created an indentation of the medial part of the edge (Figure 26j, Area J). On dorsal, trapezoidal and scalar negatives with DFR and DST terminations in diagonal direction have affected the edge similarly to PUA I (Figure 26k, Area K). PUA II was used for scraping activities with dorsal as its contact face, although the wear traces on its medial part indicate occasional cutting/sawing as well. The morphology of the scars points towards a middle-hard working material, e.g. wood. The almost complete absence of residues suggests that this tool was not used for hafting/retooling, perhaps except for the proximal end where few pitch residues might indicate such an activity.

2. Refitted Artefacts with wear traces

Series B5-317 + B6-67 + C5-31 + C5-73 + C5-86 + C5-89 + C5-90 + C5-131 + C5-141 + C5-596 + C5-620 + C5-662 + C7-53 + D5-1207 + D5-1231 + D5-1255 + D7-15

Only two artefacts of this larger series of refitted artefacts from Ullafelsen showed identifiable wear traces.

B6: 67 (Figure 27a): The flake's edge PUA I shows a distinctive reduction caused by several scars and burin-like negatives (Figure 27b). The degree of edge reduction is especially prominent if the flake is put at its original position on the core (Figure 27c). Hafting residues cover the edge (Figure 27d, Area A) while the coarse surface structure of the chert barely shows any micropolish. Only at Pos. 1 appear some GWP spots, probably caused by contact with a shaft (Figure 27e). The opposite edge shows no retouch but is as well covered by residue streaks. Few small scars on the immediate edge seem to be associated with the residues. They appear as PST-DFR negatives (Figure 27f, Area B), respectively with PSH-DST cross-section (Figure 27g, Area C), in transverse orientation. This flake was probably used as a hafted projectile implement.

C5: 131 (Figure 28a): This delicate bladelet fits on C5-662 + C7-53. Its lateral edge PUA I is almost undamaged while lateral edge PUA II appears slightly serrated, caused by several PBS-DFR microscars located alternately on ventral and dorsal (Figure 28b, Area A; Figure 28c, Area B). Some scars appear with a "clean" surface and, therefore, can be considered to be post-depositional. The distal end has a significant reduction of ca. 4mm, when compared to its

negative on the refitted part (C5-662 + C7-53). It bears a scraper-like retouch composed of very steep scars with PST-DFR profile on dorsal (Figure 28d, Area C). No secondary scars are visible on the retouched distal end and its ventral face is undamaged. The surface around the distal end seems rather fresh and shows no micropolish (Figure 28e, Pos. 2). Blackish residues are speckled along PUA II on dorsal and ventral as well (Figure 28f, Area D). Under the reflected-light microscope, single droplets of pitch are visible (Figure 28g, Pos. 1). Despite the rather minimal presence of the residues, the sediment remains that are solidly attached to them demonstrate their adhesive capacity. The bladelet was possibly used as hafted implement. The slanted end retouch was not functionally active and could be a fitting to insert the implement in an already prepared hafting slot.

Series D5: 84 + D5: 235 + D6: 110: Three refitted fragments of a shattered piece (Figure 29a)

Especially, no. D5: 235 has significant damage caused by deep intruding breaks and scars at its PUA I (Figure 29b, Area A) that affected as well the connecting parts of D5: 84 and D6: 110. It can, therefore, be considered as use-related and happened before the fragmentation of the tool. Area A is composed of larger, and overlapping negatives. A second-edge-row developed on the concave middle part. Its scars appear rounded and show the same densely stepped orientation as the primary negatives (Figure 29c, Area B). The extension and morphology of the edge-wear indicates a harder contact material like bone or antler. Several scars of Area A carry pitch residues (Figure 29d, Area C). Vis-à-vis, an elongated fracture plane has formed along the lateral edge PUA II (Figure 29e, Area D). Its steep-angled edge shows only few microscars with DFR terminations. They were probably caused by a transversely oriented activity, for example scraping that was carried out with mild pressure, or the smoothing of a middle-hard material. Almost no micropolish is visible along the edge. Few isolated polish spots at the immediate edge remained undiagnostic. Their bright reflection might, at best, suggest a harder working material like wood. The concave shape of Area D would be suitable for the smoothing of a round wooden object, for instance a grip or a shaft.

Series D8: 29 + D8: 35 + C8: 896 + C8: 110 + C8: 203 + C9: 68

Only two artefacts, no. D8: 29 and D8: 35 showed identifiable use-wear. These refitted scraper fragments were already mentioned in the first volume of the Ullafelsen monograph (Schäfer 2012: 420). The scraper edge PUA I is visible rounded and was probably used for scraping and softening hide or leather. Residues of hafting pitch on some negatives of the scraper retouch might indicate a second use for the smoothing or cleaning of used and pitch covered shafts.

3 Selected artefacts from the site Kaseralmschrofen

J4: 5 (Figure 30a): This chip was originally debris from the preparation of a striking platform edge. However, its steep lateral edge shows a scraper-like retouch composed of adjoining DFR-scars (Figure 30b, Area A). Vaguely recognizable is secondary microscarring on the apex of the convex retouch that indicates the use of the artefact (Figure 30c). Micropolish is almost absent. Only single polish spots with bright reflection appear along the edge. Their slightly rough surface shows diffuse micropitting (Figure 30d, Pos. 1). Minor blackish residues that could be residues of hafting pitch are adhering to the nooks of the hinged distal end (Figure 30e, Area B). The traces suggest that this small tool was used for hafting/retooling activities.

J4: 64 (Figure 31a): This triangular flake is made of crystal rock. Its longer lateral edge has an almost 90° edge angle and bears several burin-like removals that resemble impact scars usually found on projectile implements (Figure 31b, Area A). The distal end is blunted by retouch (Figure 31c, Area B). The diagonal edge has been damaged by a crescent break and a following torsion break. Both breaks were caused by forces on the distal end (Figure 31d, Area C). The proximal end is shattered and shows multiple breaks that exceed the usual scarring of platform remnants (Figure 31e, Area D). The densely-grouped scars have primarily DHG terminations and irregular shapes. Small residue spots can be the remains of pitch suggesting hafting at the proximal part (Figure 31f). Also, the presence of a large scalar scar that reduced the dorsal face, possibly adjusting the rather thick proximal end to fit into a hafting slot (Figure 31g, Area E) supports the interpretation as a small projectile point.

J4: 66 (Figure 32a): This circular scraper has retouched areas on dorsal and ventral. Area A shows a rather shallow convex retouch with a weakly developed second-edge-row at its apex (Figure 32b). Some minor residues in the corners of the scars are probably the remains of hafting pitch (Figure 32c). The lesser curved Area B has several stages of retouch that indicate the re-sharpening of the scraper edge. The primary scraper retouches have PST-DFR cross-sections, except on the apex where less regular shaped and stepped DHG scars appear (Figure 32d). A “micro-second-edge-row” appears together with residues on Area B (Figure 32e). The potentially used areas PUA III and IV on the opposite side indicate hafting. Pitch residues can be found on Area D (Figure 32f) and Area E (Figure 32g) while Area C shows a facial reduction of the dorsal face, possibly intentionally carried out to fit that part of the tool into a hafting slot. (Figure 32h). It is therefore likely, that this scraper has two corresponding functional and hafting areas reflecting two stages of use. Unfortunately, the high power analysis was hampered by sediment polish that covered the entire tool’s surface and prevented the observation of any diagnostic micropolish (Figure 32i, Pos. 1; Figure 32j, Pos. 2).

J5: 51 (Figure 33): The shape of this shattered fragment resembles a projectile point at first sight. A closer look, however, revealed that this is caused by multiple fractures only and no use-wear traces were detected along the still sharp edges.

J5: 80 (Figure 34a): A thumbnail scraper made of an igneous rock that was considerably reduced until its length became shorter than its width. The final modification appears rather irregular and created a serrated scraper edge (Figure 34b). No ventral scars nor any rounding of the scraper edge appear, so that it seems that the tool was discarded soon after the last re-sharpening of the scraper edge, probably due to the very short stage. No micropolish can be detected and the sole indication for the use of this edge are barely visible secondary scars with DST- und DHG-cross-sections at the immediate edge of the scraper retouch (Figure 34c, Area A). Additionally, a slight abrasion occurs on some ridges (Figure 34d, Area B). Signs of a former hafting appear on the dorsal ridges where significant rounding (Figure 34e, Area C). This abrasion might have been caused by the contact with a shaft. No residues are visible; however, numerous hornblende intrusions hamper the recognition of pitch residues. The very limited wear on the functional part of the tool does not permit the identification of the contact material.

J5: 86 (Figure 35a): This scraper fragment shows heavy fracturing. Only a part of the former scraper edge remained intact (Figure 35b, Area A). It is severely abraded by multiple second-edge-row scars (Figure 35c, Area B). A strong post-depositional sediment polish prevents mostly the high power analysis. Only at Pos. 1 is micropolish with diffuse micropitting and bright reflection visible that developed on elevated parts of the micro-topography (Figure 35d).

The extensive second-edge-row and the micropolish indicate a harder contact material. No hafting traces were observed on this fragment.

J5-107 (Figure 36a): This is a very delicate, elongated micro point with triangular cross-section. Both lateral edges have steep retouches on dorsal. The proximal end was modified into a sharp tip while the hinged distal end was turned into the base. Although the retouches appear irregular due to the inhomogeneous and fissured raw material (Figure 36b, Area A), was the point thoroughly manufactured. The proximal end appears largely undamaged, except for the immediate tip that is thinned by a diagonal shear fracture (Figure 36c, Area B). No scars appear on the ventral face. Polish spots with a rough, blotting-paper structure and diffuse longitudinal striations have developed on the tip (Figure 36d, Pos. 2). Small pitch residues are scattered mainly on the distal part of the artefact (Figure 36e, Area C), indicating a basal hafting of the tip but appear at the tip as well.

Noticeable are larger reductions along the dorsal ridge that affected the distal (Figure 36f, Area D) and even stronger the proximal part of the tool (Figure 36g, Area E), but left out the medial area. This might hint to a previous reworking of the tool. It is possible that the proximal part was initially the hafted area, prior to its modification into a pointed end. Hafting micropolish on elevated areas of the micro-topography associated with small residue spots provide further evidence for such assumption (Figure 36h, Pos. 1). The appearance and distribution of wear traces and residues indicate the use as a projectile point, possibly reworked and used in two stages with interchanging functional parts.

J5: 110 (Figure 37a): This triangular microlith was made of transparent crystal rock. It received its form already during the removal from the core, without much necessity for further modification. Almost half of the lateral edge PUA I is reduced by a slightly distorted elongated scar on ventral, similar to a burin negative and initiated at the proximal end (Figure 37b, Area A). The distal end (PUA II) shows delicate abrasions on the right-angled corner (Figure 37c, Area B), and wide crescent breaks with a limited depth of penetration (Figure 37d, Area C). They are followed by an inverted hinge fracture on dorsal (Figure 37e, Area D). The proximal end has on dorsal several scars with DST termination initiated from the platform remnant, possibly the result of the reduction of a platform overhang. Some pitch residues appear in the corners of those negatives (Figure 37f, Area E) and, less obvious, also on the distal hinge fracture at Area F (Figure 37g). The residues indicate hafting along the shorter lateral edge PUA III, creating a “delta wing”-like position of the triangle in the shaft (Figure 37h). The burin-like reduction of PUA III can, therefore, be interpreted as impact scar. The edge wear on Area D was possibly non-intentional and caused by handling or contacts with other implements. It is also possible that upon impact reacting forces pushed the hafting implement backwards hitting another lateral implement that was hafted next to it.

J6: 9 (Figure 38a): A rectangular flake with retouch on both lateral edges. The distal end was removed by a slightly oblique hinge fracture. The somewhat retracted Area A bears a sequence of trapezoidal scars with DST and DHG terminations on the dorsal face of PUA I (Figure 38b). Towards distal, the scars appear more alternating on dorsal and ventral (Figure 38c, Area B). Along the proximal part of PUA II is a row of delicate retouches visible on dorsal. It appears slightly irregular and serrated, probably caused by the undulated relief of the ventral face (Figure 38d, Area C). The distal part of the edge was damaged by a transverse fracture initiated from the distal end (Figure 38e, Area D). Only few residues are visible possibly the remains of hafting pitch. They appear on the negatives of PUA I (Figure 38f, Area E) and at the jagged platform remnant but are not very diagnostic (Figure 38g, Area F). In context with the distal scars, they might point to a use of the tool as laterally hafted implement. The natural reflection of the tool's surface caused by embedded radiolarian microfossils affects the high power

analysis (Figure 38h, Pos. 1) and hampered a recognition of potential weakly developed micropolish like hafting polish. Almost no micropolishes appear along the lateral edges. Only Pos. 2 displays a bright reflecting polish zone with smooth and domed structure slight micropitting and vaguely visible longitudinal striations, characteristic for a contact with bone (Figure 38i) and probably caused by the use as projectile implement and contacts with bone upon impact.

J6: 10 (Figure 39a): This scraper has been reduced almost until the bulb due to continuous re-sharpening (Figure 39b, Area A). A diagonal vein filled with quartz runs across the tool and ends in a protruding tip at the scraper edge (Area B), while the edge was reduced towards both sides of the vein. Obviously, an attempt was made to remove or at least reduce that protruding area by grinding the hard and resistant quartz during the re-sharpening process (Figure 39c, Area B), demonstrating the exploitation of this tool. At the zenith of the convex scraper edge appears a second-edge-row (Figure 39d, Area C). The smooth and semi-opaque surface of the scrapers shows only few residue spots at the proximal part, indicating hafting of the base (Figure 39e, Area D). The functional edge exhibits a dull micropolish with a domed and rumped structure (Figure 39f, Pos. 1), and sometimes spots with a “fibrous” appearance on prominent parts of the micro-topography (Figure 39g, Pos. 2). This type of polish together with the slight rounding of the edge indicate the working of hide or leather. On the dorsal retouch appear weakly developed polish spots with bright reflection and an initial reticular pattern. They show diffuse deep and shallow striations perpendicular to the edge, caused by contact with a harder material. The wear traces suggest an use of this scraper for the working multiple materials. While probably the processing of skins was the dominant activity, occasionally a middle-hard or harder material was worked with it as well (Figure 39h, 39i, Pos. 3). The scraper was very likely used hafted as suggested by pitch residues but also considering the handling of such a short scraper.

K4: 18 (Figure 40a): An irregular shaped chip that appears to have sheared away from a larger artefact at a shallow angle. It has a bent backed retouch at its lateral edge PUA I (Figure 40b, Area A). The opposite concave PUA II appears slightly serrated caused by a loosely connected row of trapezoidal PSH-DST scars on both sides of the edge (Figure 40c, Area B; Figure 40d, Area C). It is possible that they were not caused by using the thin and fragile state of the edge but are rather of taphonomic origin. No micropolish was observed and a use of this small artefact remains uncertain.

K4: 117 (Figure 41a): A scraper, reduced to ‘thumbnail’ size by successive re-sharpening (Figure 41b and 41c, Area A). The front of the scraper was blunted by second-edge-row composed of diffuse microscars that are even at higher magnifications above 20x hardly recognizable on the semi-opaque to almost transparent flint along the edge (Figure 41d, Area B). The scraper edge barely shows any sign of rounding. No scars appear on ventral, the few negatives at the fringes of the convex scraper edge seem to be post-depositional (Figure 41e, Area C). Beyond the immediate edge appear dull reflecting micropolishes with a rumped and smudgy structure that occasionally developed into dense and smoother polish spots (Figure 41f, Pos. 1). Short and diffuse striations appeared perpendicular to the edge (Figure 41g, Pos. 2). The scraper retouch bears few GWP polish zones with smudgy structures (Figure 41h, Pos. 5). These polishes point to the working of skin and hide. However, blackish residues found on some retouch negatives might be the remains of hafting pitch and suggest the working of used and pitch stained shafts (Figure 41i, Area D). Very few residues remained on the proximal part of the tool. They appear as smallest dark spots on the surface that can hardly distinguished from blackish dot-shaped intrusions within the transparent flint (Figure 41j, Area E). A stronger indication for hafting are reticular polish patterns that developed mainly on elevated parts of

the micro-topography (Figure 41k, Pos. 3), including the bulb of percussion (Figure 41l, Pos. 4). The wear and extensive size reduction of the scraper indicate a prolonged use of this tool on various materials. It was probably also carried together with other siliceous items as suggested by the appearance of some bright spots on ventral (Figure 41m, Pos. 6).

K4: 118 (Figure 42a): This is a small scraper that was reworked from a former burin. The asymmetric scraper retouch is located on the proximal end and along one lateral edge (Figure 42b, Area A). Area B still shows the remnants of the former burin facet, partially displaced by the scraper retouch (Figure 42c). The proximal part of the scraper was re-sharpened (Figure 42d, Area C). A weakly second-edge-row composed of diffuse microscars Area D indicates a middle-hard to harder contact material (Figure 42e, Area D). In addition, micropolish clings to the surface relief along the scraper's edge on ventral. Its structure and greasy appearance are characteristic for the working of hide and leather (Figure 42f, Pos. 1), very similar to the micropolish observed on the above-mentioned scraper no K4:117. Numerous shallow and diffuse striations perpendicular to the edge evidence a transversely oriented handling of the tool (Figure 42g). The edge appears slightly rounded at higher magnification. No scars appear on the ventral face. The dorsal face shows some breaks and fissures on its proximal part. Minor residues are preserved within some fissures of the surface (Figure 42h, Area E). Similar to K4-117, reticular micropolish that affect elevated parts of the microtopography appear (Figure 42i, Pos. 2) associated with residue spots (Figure 42j, Pos. 3). The polish patterns and residues suggest a hafting of this scraper.

K5: 28 (Figure 43a): This core fragment has at its distal end remnants of a retouch (Figure 43b, Area A). An initial second-edge-row of trapezoidal microscars with DST termination has formed on scalar negatives with PBS-DFR cross-section of the retouch, probably as a result of re-sharpening (Figure 43c, Area B). This tool could be a fragment of a scraper that was used for working harder materials. However, no micropolish was detected. Therefore, it is possible that the tool was either used only for a short period, or it was discarded very soon after the last re-sharpening process and the removing of potential edge polish during the reduction of the working edge.

L4: 9 (Figure 44a): This scraper has a steep profile and a pointed base, possibly caused by transverse fractures of the lateral edges that were consequently reworked and modified to a keel-scraper form (Figure 44b, Area A). Protruding remains of previous retouch negatives give evidence to significant re-sharpening and reduction of the scraper edge (Figure 44c, Area B). The most intensive abrasion of the scraper appears on the averted shorter leg of the asymmetric scraper edge (Figure 44d, Area C). This might as well indicate a reworking of the scraper after its lateral fracturing. Along the edge appears a weak polish that occasionally includes better developed polish spots with bright reflection, smooth and blotting-paper surfaces and carrying diffuse micropitting (Figure 44e, Pos. 1; Figure 44f, Pos. 2). In context with the edge wear, the polish pattern suggests the working of a harder material. Residues embedded in the negatives at Area C indicate a hafting/retooling activity, for example the re-working or repair of used shafts (Figure 44g). Abrasions and scarring along the dorsal ridge might have resulted from the contact of the narrow base with a shaft (Figure 44h, Area D; Figure 44i, Area E). Although no hafting residues are visible, a reticular patterned generic-weak micropolish that appears on elevated parts of the micro-topography supports a hafted use of this scraper (Figure 44j, Pos. 3).

L4: 10 (Figure 45a): This artefact is a distal fragment of a backed bladelet. The steep-angled edge was modified by a regular backed retouch on dorsal. A slight blunting of the immediate edge was caused by a delicate second-edge-row, possibly carried out to chamfer the edge thus

providing it with greater stability (Figure 45b, Area A). While the edge modification also covers the tip of the tool, the straight lateral edge remained unretouched. The very few observed trapezoidal micro-scars might not be use-related (Figure 45c, Area B). This fragment broke off with a straight bending fracture with hinge termination (Figure 45d, Area C). There are no further damages visible on the artefact and no residues and hafting polish were detected. The immediate tip is slightly rounded and shows developed polish spots with a smooth, undulating structure, micropitting and short diffuse striations that are longitudinally oriented to the tool's axis (Figure 45e, Pos. 1). More developed polish spots with bright reflection and the same smooth micropitting structure appear near the dorsal ridge (Figure 45f, Pos. 2; Figure 45g Pos. 3). The micropolish is characteristic for the contact with bone. It could have been created by a dynamic contact with bone upon penetration of an animal's carcass. A use of this artefact as a projectile point with the missing base as hafted area can, therefore, be considered.

Conclusion

In total, 82 artefacts from Ullafelsen and 22 artefacts from Kaseralmschrofen were subjected to a microscopic use-wear analysis. The selection from Ullafelsen included unmodified artefacts with wear traces and complements a previously conducted microwear study of formal tools and retouched artefacts from this site (Pawlik 2011). Fifty-eight out of the 82 specimens from Ullafelsen did not show any identifiable use-wear traces. However, 24 artefacts and almost one fourth of all unmodified pieces and fragments were identified as being used as tools (Table 2). All artefacts with wear traces had multiple functional areas, 17 specimens had two, and one specimen each even had three, respectively four functional areas. Residues of hafting adhesives appeared on 18 out of the 24 unmodified artefacts with use traces. This is more or less equivalent to the results from the use-wear analysis of the modified tools and the previous Ullafelsen Volume 1 already discussed the importance of hafting technology in this context (Pawlik 2011). The hafting adhesive used at Ullafelsen was probably manufactured by dry distillation of birch bark (see Pawlik 2011: 404ff). Among the tools with hafting residues were nine projectile implements and nine working tools. Of the latter, three carried pitch residues on their functionally active parts. This suggests that they were used for the maintenance and repair of composite tools, including the reworking of used and pitch-stained shaft slots ("hafting-and-retooling"), rather than being themselves hafted. Lumps of birch pitch found in the sediment of Ullafelsen demonstrated that the adhesive was directly produced on site (Pawlik 2011). The analyzed artefacts from the nearby Kaseralmschrofen were used for activities similar as those already observed on the Ullafelsen assemblage. Although the small overall number of the assemblage restricts the interpretation regarding site functions, the presence of several hide working tools could suggest that preparation of animal skin and the repair of leather items took place. The site's immediate proximity to the Fotsch river surely was favorable for the processing of hide and skins which requires a water source.

The functional analysis of the unmodified artefacts from Ullafelsen showed that sites and lithic industries that are characterized by complex composite tool production like the Central European Mesolithic with its wide range of geometric forms had as well a significant amount of unmodified débitage incorporated in the toolkit. This included even artefacts that would have considered as debris and production waste based on morphological and technological analysis (see Hahn 1993: 156ff). Traceological analysis, on the other hand, shows that such artefacts had the potential to be used as tools as well, and independent of their sizes and shapes. This is even more the case if those artefacts were the parts of complex composite tools (Keeley 1982; Vaughan 1985; Ambrose 2010; Pawlik 2012). This analysis identified not only geometric microliths as hafted implements but unmodified artefacts as well. They were intentionally selected and attached to shafts without any further modification. The majority of the analysed

artefacts at Ullafelsen, show traces of such a use providing further credit to the fundamental rule of Semenov (1964) that not only formal tool types were used in Prehistory but that any lithic artefact with potentially used areas may carry use traces and, therefore, must be considered a tool.

Bibliography

Ambrose, Stanley H., 2010: Coevolution of Composite-Tool Technology, Constructive Memory, and Language - Implications for the Evolution of Modern Human Behavior. *Current Anthropology* 51 (S1): 135-147.

Fischer, Anders, Peter Vemming Hansen and Peter Rasmussen, 1984: Macro and micro wear traces on lithic projectile points: experimental results and prehistoric examples. *Journal of Danish Archaeology* 3: 19-46.

Keeley, Lawrence H., 1982. Hafting and Retooling: Effects in the Archaeological Record. *American Antiquity* 47: 798-809.

Hahn, Joachim, 1993: *Erkennen und Bestimmen von Stein- und Knochenartefakten. Einführung in die Artefaktmorphologie*. Archaeologica Venatoria 10. Tübingen.

Hayden, Brian (ed.) 1979: *Lithic Usewear Analysis*. Academic Press. New York.

Levi-Sala, Irene, 1996: *A Study of Microscopic Polish on Flint Implements*. British Archaeological Reports Series 629.

Pawlik, Alfred, 2011. Functional Analysis of the stone tools and the reconstruction of activities at the Mesolithic site of Ullafelsen. In: D. Schäfer (ed.), *Das Mesolithikum-Projekt Ullafelsen. Mensch und Umwelt im Holozän Tirols 1*: 319-424. Philipp von Zabern. Innsbruck 2011

Pawlik, Alfred, 2012. Behavioural Complexity and Modern Traits in the Philippine Upper Palaeolithic. *Asian Perspectives* 51 (1): 22-46.

Schäfer, Dieter (ed.), 2011: *Das Mesolithikum-Projekt Ullafelsen. Mensch und Umwelt im Holozän Tirols 1*: 319-424. Philipp von Zabern. Innsbruck 2011.

Semenov, Sergej A., 1964: *Prehistoric Technology*. Adams and Dart. Bath.

Telle, Rainer, 2011: Silikatische Rohstoffe aus dem eiszeitlichen Camp Altdorf – Stelle 113, „Präkeramik“ aus dem 120. Jtsd zur Erschmelzung von Birkenpech. Unpubl. Prüfungsbericht GA-Nr. 3261, Institut für Gesteinshüttenkunde, Lehrstuhl für Keramik und feuerfeste Werkstoffe, Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen.

Unrath, Günther, Linda R. Owen, Annelou van Gijn, Emily H. Moss, Hugues Plisson, and Patrick Vaughan, 1986: An evaluation of micro-wear studies: A multi-analyst approach. In Unrath, G. & Owen L. (Eds.), *Technical Aspects of Micro-wear Studies on Stone Tools*. *Early Man News* 9/10/11: 117-176. Archaeologica Venatoria. Tübingen.

Vaughan, Patrick, 1985: *Use-wear Analysis of Flaked Stone Tools*. University of Arizona Press. Tucson.

Table 2: Artefacts from Ullafelsen and Kaseralmschrofen selected for microscopic use: wear analysis

Ullafelsen: unmodified and refitted artefacts							
Number	Morphology	PUA	Direction of use	Contact material	Function	Residues	Function/Context
B5: 64	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 102	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 117	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 200	Point	2	longitudinal	Projectile?	Projectile point?	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
B5: 231	Flake	2	longitudinal			y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
B5: 245	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 352	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 395,1: 2	Blade	2	longitudinal	Projectile	Projectile implement	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
B5: 396	Point	2	longitudinal	soft	hafted working tool	y	Processing of hide/leather
B5: 397	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B5: 435	Blade fragment	2	indeterminable			y	hafting and retooling
B6: 20	Burin	2	longitudinal	Projectile	Projectile implement	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
B6: 135	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B6: 163	Blade	2	longitudinal	soft	hafted working tool	y	Processing softer material
B6: 168	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B7: 210	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B7: 538	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 99	Flake	2	longitudinal	soft: middle hard	Working tool	n	Processing softer material
B8: 147	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 202	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 243	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 257	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 508	Point	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 511	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
B8: 649	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C4: 12	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C4: 23	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C4: 138	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C4: 175	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 30	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 88	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 97	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 482	Burin spall	3	multiple	middle hard	Working tool	y	hafting and retooling
C5: 517	Point	1	Rotation	soft	Working tool	n	Processing of hide/leather
C5: 554	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 568	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a

C5: 657	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C5: 707	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C6: 4	Burin spall	1	multiple	middle hard	Working tool	y	hafting and retooling
C6: 10	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C6: 23	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C6: 28	Flake	2	transversal	hard organic	hafted working tool	y	hafting and retooling
C6: 108	Point	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C6: 116	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C6: 118	Flake	1	transversal	middle hard	Working tool	n	Processing middle hard material
C6: 122	Flake	1	longitudinal	hard organic	Working tool	n	Processing harder material
C6: 122	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C7: 23	Point	2	longitudinal	Projectile?	Projectile point?	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
C7: 36	Flake	2	transversal	Projectile?	Transverse projectile head?	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
C7: 150	Point	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C7: 212	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C7: 347	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 29	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 123	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 286	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 405	Shatter	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 405	Burin	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 555	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C8: 1209	Point	2	multiple	middle hard	Multifunktion	y	Scraping and grooving, context with hafting and retooling activity
C9: 147	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
C9: 649	Blade	2	longitudinal	Projectile	Projectile implement	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
D4: 205	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D4: 212	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D4: 234	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D5: 192	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D5: 218	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D5: 308	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D5: 344	Splintered piece	4	multiple	hard organic	Multifunctional	n	Chisel use and cutting activity
D5: 347	Blade	2				y	hafting and retooling
D5: 588	Point	2	longitudinal	Projectile?	Projectile point?	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
D5: 1229	Scraper	2	transversal	soft	hafted working tool	y	Processing of hide/leather
D5: 1470	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D6: 50	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D6: 292	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D7: 9	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D7: 15	Burin spall	1			Engraving tool?	y	Processing harder material

D8: 21	Blade	2				y	Multifunctional; hafting and retooling.
D8: 60	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
D8: 77	Blade fragment	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
E6: 149	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
E8: 5	Flake	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a
F7: 70	Blade	0	no microwear traces			n	n/a

Kaseralschrofen: modified and unmodified artefacts with potentially used areas							
J4: 5	Chip	1	indeterminable	hard organic	working tool	y	hafting and retooling
J4: 8	Shatter	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
J4: 54	Platform remnant	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
J4: 64	Flake	1	longitudinal	projectile	projectile	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
J4: 66	Scraper	2	transversal	indeterminable	hafted working tool	y	Processing unspecified material
J5: 51	Shatter	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
J5: 80	Scraper	1	transversal	indeterminable	hafted working tool	n	Processing unspecified material
J5: 86	Scraper	1	transversal	hard organic	working tool	n	Processing unspecified material
J5: 99	Flake	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
J5: 107	Micropoint	1	longitudinal	projectile	projectile	y	hafting and retooling
J5: 110	Triangular microlith	1	longitudinal	projectile	projectile	y	hafting and retooling
J6: 5	Core fragment	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
J6: 9	Flake	2	longitudinal	projectile	projectile	y	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling
J6: 10	Scraper	1	transversal	multiple	hafted working tool	y	Working of hide/leather and unspecified harder material
K4: 18	Chip	?	indeterminable	indeterminable	indeterminable	n	
K4: 117	Scraper	1	transversal	multiple	hafted working tool	y	Working of hide/leather and hafting/retooling
K4: 118	Scraper	1	transversal	multiple	hafted working tool	y	Working of hide/leather and unspecified harder material
K5: 28	Core fragment	1	transversal	hard organic	working tool	n	Processing of a harder material
K5: 35	Shatter	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
K5: 179	Flake	0	no microwear traces	n/a		n	
L4: 9	Scraper	1	transversal	hard organic	hafted working tool	y	Processing of a harder material
L4: 10	Backed bladelet	1	longitudinal	projectile	projectile	n	Projectile implement, hafting and retooling